

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	2010	B		Min: 63.2191 Max: 63.4829	1165 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 580/581 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *Yellowish, silty soil south*

Covered by SU: 1016 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery M <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nails R <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles R <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sand <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Silt <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay 10% silt 80% sand 10% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
			Compaction	Color
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <i>Orange</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1016	Covers: 1173
Is cut by: 1155, 1164	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: *Dark orange/yellow layer with inclusions of white pebbles*

Δ 143 = Bronze coin + Δ 138 = small find Bronze object - Metal slag found -

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: *Situated on the South-West of Area B - South of wall 1135 East of wall 1162.*

Shape: *Rectangular shape stretching from West to East.*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions): *Light slope from West to East. Visible inclusions of medium pebbles.*

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

Have to find out tomorrow → found out that it is 1165 too!

SOUTH-END OF AREA B

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

*Silty accumulation layer above an earthen floor,
e.g. layer of floor preparation.*

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets): ?

Sample quantity (buckets): 2

Sample fraction (%): 0,005!

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by *Morgane*

on *12/10/07 12/07/10*

Revised by *CHM*

on *18.7.2010*

PDFd by *JJM*

on *21.7.2010*

Entered by

on